

ANALYSIS OF CRACK PROPAGATION IN POLYMERIC STRUCTURES

A. Ramsaroop¹, K. Kanny¹ and S. Pillay²

¹*Department of Mechanical Engineering, Durban Institute of Technology, Durban 4001, South Africa*

²*Department of Mechanical Engineering, TAFE, Central Subiaco Campus, Perth, Western Australia*

ABSTRACT

In many applications of polymeric laminated composites, the structure is subjected to cyclic loading. The understanding of crack initiation, crack propagation and crack path and the prediction thereof, in laminated composites, will enable safe use in commercial applications. This paper analyses crack behaviour in polymeric structures by utilising four testing procedures, namely, tensile, single edge notch beam (SENB), double cantilever beam (DCB) and mixed mode bending (MMB). Composite panels were manufactured using a modified vacuum bagging technique as well as a compression moulding technique. The crack initiation, crack propagation, crack path, strain energy release rates and stress intensity factors of polymeric composite structures are discussed in this study to enable the further investigation of cyclic loading of polymeric laminated composites.

KEYWORDS: continuous fibre, crack propagation, thermoplastic structures, S2 woven fibre, mixed mode bending, strain energy release rate

1. INTRODUCTION

Fibre-reinforced laminated composite structures are currently being used in a variety of engineering applications because of its high strength to weight ratio, high stiffness and good resistance to fatigue and corrosion properties [1-3]. A common problem with thermosetting structures, however, is the occurrence of delamination along ply interfaces. This failure mode may be attributed to voids emanating from the exothermic reaction associated with resin matrix, poor adhesion properties between matrix and fibre, fabrication defects and delamination due to impact loading.

Typically, when a thermosetting or thermoplastic structure is subjected to cyclic loading, minute cracks occur. Upon sustained loading, these cracks coalesce to form a primary crack, which invariably leads to catastrophic failure. If the crack initiation, crack propagation and crack path can be predicted then catastrophic failure may be contained, either by arresting or redirecting the crack path. A better understanding of the behaviour of crack propagation in laminated composites will enable safe and proper use in commercial applications.

To facilitate the investigation of crack behaviour in polymeric structures under cyclic loading, certain material properties need to be known. These include the stiffness, strain energy release rates and stress intensity factors. This paper involves the study of these parameters by subjecting polymeric laminated composites to tensile, single edge notch beam (SENB), double cantilever beam (DCB) and mixed mode bending (MMB) tests.

Mode I and Mode II fracture mechanisms can be determined from the double cantilever beam (DCB) and end notch flexure (ENF) tests, respectively. In practice, however, polymeric structures do not experience pure Mode I or Mode II delamination but rather a mixture of these modes. Hence, the MMB test, a combination of the DCB and ENF loadings, was developed to investigate crack growth in polymeric structures due to both Mode I and Mode II delamination. An in-house MMB test fixture was designed and constructed in accordance with work carried out by Donald F. Adams et al [5] and J.R. Reeder et al [6].

The results obtained from the different tests were recorded and used to calculate the Young's modulus (E), stress intensity factor (K) and the strain energy release rate (G). These values were then utilised to plot various graphs. Photographs of the test coupons during and after testing were also taken. SEM analysis was also conducted on the tested coupons.

2. MANUFACTURING

Thermosetting composite panels were manufactured using a vacuum bagging technique while a modified compression moulding process [4] was used to manufacture thermoplastic panels. An in-house fixture for the compression moulding process was designed and constructed. After manufacturing, the panels were then cut, using a band saw, into test coupons using various ASTM testing standards [5]. These coupons were then subjected to tensile, single edge notch beam (SENB), double cantilever beam (DCB) and mixed mode bending (MMB) tests.

Vacuum Bagging Technique

This process was utilised to make thermosetting panels comprising of LR20 epoxy resin and S2 woven glass mat, with fibre orientation of 0° and 90°. Conventional vacuum bagging techniques utilise a resin bath. The fibres are laid out and a vacuum bag is placed over them. Resin is then sucked from the bath and through the fibres via a vacuum pump. This process, although extensively used, yields an uneven distribution of resin as some of the fibres are not properly wetted. This technique was modified by using glass sheets and a lay-up process. The fibre mat was placed on a sheet of glass and resin was poured onto it. The resin was then spread out to ensure good wetting. Thereafter, another layer of the fibre mat was placed on top of the wetted fibre mat and more resin was added. This continued until the required number of layers was achieved. A second glass sheet was then placed on top of the resin-fibre composite. The wetted glass mat, now sandwiched between the two glass sheets, was vacuum bagged. In addition to the vacuum sucking out the excess resin, it also induced compression between the glass sheets. Hence, an even distribution of resin, lower void content, as well as a good surface finish was achieved. The panel itself comprised of 12 layers of woven glass fibre. The final thickness of the panel was 3.5 mm.

Compression Moulding Technique

Thermoplastic panels were manufactured using a modified compression moulding technique. Two types of panels were made, namely, polypropylene and continuous random S2 glass fibre mat, and, polypropylene and S2 woven glass mat as in the vacuum bagging process. Both were manufactured using the same method. Polypropylene pellets were placed on a plate that was gradually heated to 170 °C. Upon complete transition of the pellets into the liquid phase, the S2 glass mat was placed on top of the melted polypropylene. The glass mat was then evened out to ensure no wrinkling as well as to allow the plastic to penetrate through the fibre mat. Thereafter, another layer of plastic pellets were placed on the now wetted S2 glass mat.

Once this layer of pellets was melted, the process was repeated until the required number of glass layers was achieved. A second heated plate, also at 170 °C, was used to compress the composite via a hydraulic press. The compression ensured proper wetting of the fibres and an even distribution of plastic. Both types of panels consisted of 4 layers of glass fibre with a final thickness of 5.5 mm. In the case of the polypropylene and S2 woven glass mat, the fibre volume was determined to be 13 %.

3. TESTING PROCEDURES

Specimens were cut from the manufactured panels and subjected to the following tests: tensile, single edge notch beam (SENB), double cantilever beam (DCB) and mixed mode bending (MMB). All testing was carried out on a Lloyds tensile tester.

Tensile

Specimens were cut to dimensions in accordance with the ASTM D 3039 / D 3039M – 93 testing standard. The stiffness (E) was determined.

SENB

The test coupons were subjected to a three point bend test with compliance to the ASTM D 790 – 81 test standard. From this test, the load, extension, crack length (a) and time were recorded, and the fracture toughness (K) was determined using the following equation [7]:

$$K = \sigma \sqrt{\pi a} \quad (1)$$

DCB

ASTM D 5528 was the test standard used for this type of testing. The load, time and crack length were recorded and the Mode I fracture toughness (K_I) was calculated using equation 1.

MMB

A fixture for this test was designed and manufactured in-house. The testing standard used for the test coupons was ASTM D 6671. The load, extension, crack length and time were recorded. These values were used to determine the strain energy release rate (G) using the equation [5, 7, 8] shown below.

$$G = G_I + G_{II} \quad (2)$$

where: G_I and G_{II} are the strain energy release rates for the Mode I and Mode II components respectively and are given by:

$$G_I = \frac{12P_I^2(a+xh)^2}{w^2h^3E_1} \quad (3)$$

$$G_{II} = \frac{9P_{II}^2(a+0.42xh)^2}{16w^2h^3E_1} \quad (4)$$

In equations (3) and (4) a is the crack length, w is the width of the coupon, and h is half the thickness of the coupon. P_I and P_{II} are the opening and shearing components of the applied load [5] and are given by:

$$P_I = P \left(\frac{3c-L}{4L} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$P_{II} = P \left(\frac{c + L}{L} \right) \quad (6)$$

where: P is the applied load, L is the length of the specimen, and c is the distance from the midpoint of the coupon to the loading point. The x value in equations (3) and (4) is a correction factor and is calculated by [5]:

$$x = \left[\frac{E_1}{11G_{13}} \left(3 - 2 \left(\frac{\Gamma}{\Gamma + 1} \right)^2 \right) \right]^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

where:

$$\Gamma = 1.18 \frac{\sqrt{E_1 E_2}}{G_{13}} \quad (8)$$

Equations (7) and (8) have the value G_{13} , which is the shear modulus in fibre plane 1-3, and this is approximately equal to G_{12} [5], which is given by:

$$\frac{1}{G_{12}} = \frac{V_f}{G_f} + \frac{V_m}{G_m} \quad (9)$$

where: V is the volume fraction, G is the shear modulus, and subscript f is for fibre and m is for matrix.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tensile

Two types of specimens were subjected to this test, namely, polypropylene / S2 glass random fibre and polypropylene / S2 glass woven mat. A total of five specimens of each composite was tested and Stress vs Strain graphs were drawn for each one.

Figure 1: Stress vs Strain graphs for (a) polypropylene / S2 random fibre and (b) polypropylene / S2 woven fibre

Figure 1 shows the tensile response achieved for each of the composite panels. The tensile responses are approximately linear and are typical for visco-elastic materials. The average modulus for the polypropylene/S2 random fibre was found to be 560 MPa and for the polypropylene/S2 woven mat an average value of 615 MPa was calculated. These values are within 10 % of each other and there seems to be no significant difference between the random

and woven fibres. However, the woven fibre coupon carried 100 % more load than the random fibre. In the case of the woven fibres, more of the applied load is transferred to the fibres, and hence the greater load carrying capability. The random fibres only serve to hold the matrix together, thus preventing early fracture. Figure 2 shows the fractured area of the random fibre test coupon.

Figure 2: Polypropylene / S2 random fibre test coupon after tensile test showing (a) front view and (b) side view.

The fracture of the test coupon shown in the above figure occurred instantaneously; however, it did begin at points A and B. This is shown by the crazing on the coupon, which indicates a greater stress concentration here as there was very little fibre content at these points. The coupon first failed at points A and B, and thereafter there was catastrophic failure through the specimen. This occurred instantaneously as there was not enough material to withstand the applied load.

The test coupon shown in Figure 2 displays a fracture that is angled. This angle was determined to be approximately 20° to the vertical in Figure 2a and 45° to the vertical in Figure 2b. This is due to the random fibre direction. As the load was applied, stresses were transversely induced in the coupon along the fibre edges. These loads were not large enough to break through the fibre but they were enough to rupture the matrix. The angle shown in Figure 2a is actually the path taken by these stresses through the width of the coupon. This phenomenon was not clearly apparent in the case of the woven fibre specimens.

Figure 3: Polypropylene / S2 woven fibre test coupon after tensile test showing (a) front view and (b) side view.

Comparing Figures 2a and 3a, it may be seen that the fracture paths across the width of the coupons are very different. The fracture in the case of the woven fibre (Figure 3a) looks much straighter. Here again this is due to the fibre orientation. As in the testing of the random

fibre coupon, transverse stresses were induced along the fibre edges. Similarly the fracture is the path taken by these stresses. However, due to the more structured direction of the woven fibres (0° and 90°), the fracture path is straighter. More evidence of this can be seen when comparing the fracture paths through the thickness of the coupons (Figures 2b and 3b).

In Figure 2b the fracture path is sharply angled and the fracture surface appears as a violent brittle failure. The fracture in Figure 3b appears to follow a gentler angle and this path is not directly through the coupon. The fracture first propagated directly through the matrix and then ran along the matrix-fibre interface before going through the fibre mat. This shows that a more structured fibre direction (woven fibre composite) is more fracture resistant than a random fibre one.

Figure 4: Polypropylene / S2 woven fibre coupon after tensile test showing secondary cracking on the (a) front face and (b) back face.

Closer examination of the surface of the woven fibre coupons revealed secondary cracks as shown in Figure 4. These cracks were formed during the increased application of the load and there is no apparent pattern to their locations, that is, the spacing between the cracks on all test coupons were not regular. As the loading increased, one of these cracks developed into a primary crack and failure occurred on this matrix layer. These cracks are also visible on the matrix sub-layers of the test coupon, and here as well, developed into primary cracks leading to the overall failure of the specimen. Hence, these secondary cracks that developed into primary cracks can account for the fracture path seen in Figure 3b.

Figure 5: SEM images of the fractured surface of (a) polypropylene / S2 random fibre and (b) polypropylene / S2 woven fibre test coupons after tensile test.

Both the images in Figure 5 show good fibre-matrix bonding. This is an indication of successful panel manufacturing. In addition, fibre pull-out is clearly seen for both types of test coupons.

SENB

Polypropylene / S2 glass random fibre and polypropylene / S2 glass woven mat composite test coupons were loaded using a three point bend fixture on the Lloyds tensile tester. The initial crack length for each of the specimens was set at 5 mm and the width of the specimen was 25 mm. The stress intensity factor (K) was calculated using equation (1).

Figure 6: Polypropylene / S2 random fibre showing stress vs stress intensity factor and crack length vs stress intensity factor.

In Figure 6 stress intensity factor (K) increases with increasing stress (σ) until a maximum value of 6 MPa√m is reached at 42 MPa, and thereafter it decreases to zero as the specimen became unloaded. The initial linear portion of the graph is due to zero crack growth, however, this trend changes as crack propagation starts at $K = 5.82$ MPa√m and $\sigma = 42.5$ MPa. The downward transition of the curve is a relatively smooth one and is approximately linear. This indicates that the energy accumulated during the initial loading, prior to crack propagation, is now being released at a constant rate to the cracking point.

The crack length (a) vs stress intensity factor (K) is also shown in Figure 6. Upon loading, the crack length remains constant until the applied stress reaches 42 MPa. It is here that crack growth is initiated and the stress intensity factor reaches its maximum value of 6 MPa√m. Thereafter the crack continues to grow while the applied stress reduces to zero. This portion of the response is approximately linear indicating constant crack growth, that is, growth without a rapid increase or decrease in crack growth rate. Similar features are noted in the case of the woven fibres.

Figure 7: Polypropylene / S2 woven fibre showing stress vs stress intensity factor and crack length vs stress intensity factor.

Figure 7 shows stress and crack length vs stress intensity factor for polypropylene / S2 woven fibre. These responses are very similar to the responses shown in Figure 6 with the profiles being identical. Stress intensity factor increases with increasing stress until a maximum value of $3.8 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ is reached at 28 MPa, and thereafter it decreases as the loading on the specimen decreases. The crack growth is arrested until the threshold value is reached and then the crack propagation is identical to the random fibre case. However, there is an obvious difference between the responses in the previous two figures. In Figure 7, the stress intensity factor does not return to zero, indicating that the test coupon was not fully unloaded. This is due to a “kinking” of the test coupon during testing, which is shown below in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Photographs of polypropylene / S2 woven fibre after SENB test showing (a) top edge and (b) front surface.

Figure 8a shows the “kinking” on the top edge of the test coupon, which is directly beneath the loading point and directly above the crack. This occurrence, which was not observed in the testing of the random fibre coupons, is due to the fibre orientation. In the case of the random fibre, the absorbed energy was directed to the crack front. This energy was sufficient to overcome the fibre-matrix bond and initiate crack growth. Therefore cracking occurred

easily with no significant local stresses being incurred at the loading point. However, the polypropylene / S2 woven test coupon had a more distinct fibre structure. The absorbed energy was directed to the crack front but this was not sufficient to overcome the fibre-matrix bond or the woven fibre bond. This energy needed to be redirected and thus caused a significant local stress to develop at the loading point. Although this stress was not greater than the breaking stress of the fibres, it was greater than the matrix threshold. This resulted in the matrix succumbing to the induced stress and being compressed by the testing fixture with no evidence of fibre damage.

Due to this phenomenon, the load applied by the fixture was now not directly above the crack front. The applied stress was distributed elsewhere in the coupon as depicted by the arrows in Figure 8b. Hence the specimen did not become unloaded, and thus the stress intensity factor never reached zero. The ringed portion of the photograph shows a matrix sub-layer, and it can be assumed that a similar phenomenon occurred as in the case of the tensile test, where cracks developed on each matrix layer and subsequently coalesced to form a primary crack.

Figure 9: Crack length vs time for (a) polypropylene / S2 random fibre and (b) polypropylene / S2 woven.

Figure 9 shows the crack length vs time for the random fibre and the woven fibre coupons. The responses are similar with the only distinction being the time taken to breakage. Due to the more structured layout of the woven fibres, the test coupon took a longer time to fail as the fibres arrested the crack growth. Both the responses are not linear and this was due to the difficulty of observing the crack tip. The crack growth, however, was observed to be directly beneath the loading point, typical of a Mode I crack.

DCB

Here only the epoxy / S2 woven fibre composite panel was tested. The initial crack length was set at 40 mm and the applied load reached approximately 80 N before crack propagation was initiated. The stress due to this load is 0.914 MPa. Figure 10a shows the curve of stress intensity factor (K) vs stress. As can be seen the initial response is linear and this is due to zero crack growth. Then a point is reached ($\sigma = 0.914$ MPa) when the curve goes vertical. It is here that the crack growth initiates. The stress value remains constant, as the easiest path for the crack is through the matrix and therefore no additional load is necessary for crack propagation.

Figure 10: Epoxy / S2 woven fibre DCB graphs showing (a) stress intensity factor vs stress and (b) crack length vs time.

At first the crack growth was steady, but as the crack length reached 140 mm, the crack growth rate decreased slightly as can be seen in Figure 10b. The curve itself is approximately linear and the deviation from the linear curve is due to the difficulty in determining the position of the crack tip.

MMB

Only the polypropylene / S2 woven fibre composite was subjected to the mixed mode bending test. Figure 11 shows photographs of the test coupon set up in the testing fixture.

Figure 11: Photographs of the polypropylene / S2 woven fibre test coupon showing (a) the coupon setup in the MMB fixture, and (b) a closer look at the delaminated surface.

The apparatus on the opening side of the coupon, labelled as 1 in Figure 11a, is a re-useable hinge. Conventional methods use hinges that are bonded to the specimen using some sort of adhesive. A shortcoming of this is that some of the force applied to the test coupon goes into the adhesive bond. If this bond is weak, then the hinge becomes separated from the specimen and testing has to restart. The re-useable hinge eliminates this problem by gripping the specimen directly, and this ensures that the applied force is only directed into the specimen. The side labelled 2 in Figure 11b was painted with white correction fluid to enable better detection of the crack tip.

A closer examination of the delaminated surface in Figure 11b shows a little fibre damage (ringed area). This occurred at the crack initiation point where the fibre mat was pulled out of the matrix. Thereafter there is no evidence of crack propagation through the thickness of specimen, that is, the crack path does not penetrate through any of the fibre layers. This indicates that the easiest path for the crack was through the fibre-matrix interface. Graphs of crack length vs time, strain energy release rate vs time, strain energy release rate vs crack length and strain energy release rate vs load were plotted and are shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Polypropylene / S2 woven fibre graphs showing (a) crack length vs time, (b) strain energy vs time, strain energy vs crack length, and (d) strain energy vs load.

The test results were used to calculate the strain energy release rate (G) using equations (2) to (8). The value for Young's modulus (E) was obtained from the tensile tests and G_{12} was calculated using equation (9) and was found to be 560 MPa.

The crack growth rate response, shown in Figure 12a, is initially linear until $t = 1800$ s. Then, as crack growth is initiated, the curve becomes exponential until $t = 2200$ s. During this period the crack propagation is fairly rapid with the crack growing approximately 1 mm every 30 s. Thereafter, the graph is almost linear indicating constant crack growth. The crack propagation rate decreased to approximately 1 mm every 130 s.

Figure 12b shows the strain energy release rate (G) vs time. G increases from zero to a value of 23.5 J/m^2 during which time there is no crack growth. This portion of the curve indicates that energy is being accumulated to initiate crack propagation. The graph remains relatively fixed for a while with the strain energy only increasing to 23.6 J/m^2 . During this period, crack

propagation is initiated. Thereafter, as the crack growth increases, G decreases and finally returns to zero. This process is also demonstrated in Figure 12c, where G increases to its maximum value while the crack length remains constant at $a = 25$ mm. Then G remains constant while the crack growth is initiated, and thereafter G drops to zero as the crack length increases.

The curve in Figure 12d shows the strain energy release rate vs the applied load. The graph appears to be an exponential curve starting at zero and ending at 80 N. This, however, is not the case. The curve has actually doubled back on itself. The graph starts at zero and reaches the maximum value at 80 N, and then returns to zero along the same path. In the world of physics, it is stated that energy is neither created nor destroyed but merely transformed from one form to another. This graph emphasises the previous statement by showing that, the energy accumulated before crack growth occurred, was utilised to break the initial fibre-matrix bond and then fully dissipated in the rest of the crack growth.

6. CONCLUSION

- Composite panels comprising 13% fibre of both the random and woven types were successfully manufactured using the modified vacuum bagging and compression moulding techniques.
- In all cases secondary cracking was observed on each matrix layer and these cracks coalesced to form a primary crack leading to the final failure event.
- Woven fibres structures loaded in tension are capable of carrying 100 % more load than the random fibre structures. The crack path can be predicted; however predicting location of crack initiation requires further investigation.
- For single edged notched beams :
 - ⇒ the crack initiated at the maximum stress point and the crack propagated directly across the width of the specimen.
 - ⇒ The crack propagation rate for the random fibre coupons was approximately 5 times faster than the woven fibre coupon (6mm/min opposed to 1.2mm/min) despite the maximum stress intensity factor being 1.5 times more than the woven fibre.
 - ⇒ In the woven fibre coupon, the crack arrested temporarily at the location of each of the fibres. The crack propagated approximately 95 % of the width whereupon secondary compression failure occurred.
- For Mixed Mode Bending:
 - ⇒ the crack propagation rate was 2mm/min and thereafter it decreased to 0.5mm/min. This reduction in the crack growth rate was due to the transitioning of the applied stress from a pure bending to a bending / tearing one and finally to pure tearing stress. This transfer of stress is the transition from Mode I to Mode II.
 - ⇒ The maximum strain energy release for the woven fibre coupons rate was 23.6 J/m^2 .
- Fibre orientation plays an important role in crack propagation and crack arrest. The structured fibre layout offers greater the resistance to crack growth.

7. REFERENCES

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